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Une analyse historique des machines à prévoir les marées par une approche prosopographique adaptée et des outils en humanités numériques

Résumé

L'approche prosopographique est adaptée à l'étude des "cycles de vies" d'un groupe d'objets techniques qu'on appelle des artefacts. L'approche novatrice est mise en œuvre en l'appliquant sur un groupe d'artefacts dans le but de répondre à des questions de recherche historiques. Le groupe d'artefacts choisi est composé de l'ensemble des machines à prévoir les marées, ce qui représente trente-trois machines. Les machines à prévoir les marées sont des ordinateurs analogiques qui ont été utilisés pour prédire les heures et les hauteurs des marées hautes et basses dans le monde entier de la fin des années 1800 jusqu'à leur remplacement par des outils numériques. La prosopographie des artefacts fait appel à des outils en humanités numériques et permet d'analyser les caractéristiques communes de la vie des machines à prévoir les marées. Cette approche prosopographique met en évidence le rôle important de ces machines, par leur utilisation et leur utilité au cours des siècles.

Mots clés : prévision des marées, machine à prévoir les marées, ordinateur analogique, artefact, prosopographie, humanités numériques, patrimoine maritime, paysage culturel maritime

An historic analysis of tide prediction machines using an adapted prosopographic approach and digital humanities tools

Abstract

The prosopographical approach is adapted to the study of the “life cycles” of a group of technical objects that we will call artefacts. The novel approach is put to the test by applying it to a real group of artefacts to answer historical research questions about them. The chosen group of artefacts is composed of the thirty-three tide prediction machines ever built. Tide prediction machines are analogue computers that were used to predict the times of high and low tides worldwide from the end of the 1800s up to the digital age. The artefact prosopography makes use of digital humanities tools and is successful in giving an analysis of the common features in the lives of tide prediction machines, which gives an appreciation of their importance, the extent of their use and usefulness, and an impression of the shape of their lives.

Keywords: tidal prediction, tide prediction machine, analogue computer, artefact, prosopography, digital humanities, maritime heritage, maritime cultural landscape

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This project was carried out as an assessment for the fulfilment of teaching unit AEPI8600 in Semester 8 of the Epistemology, History of Science and Technology Master's degree at the UBO. It is in line with research work carried out at the CFV on the theme of “maritime cultural landscapes and digital humanities” in collaboration with the *Centre Européen de Réalité Virtuelle* (CERV).

This introduction will explain the background to the choice of theme and methodology for the project, give a brief review of the current knowledge in these two fields, state the aims of the research and outline the following chapters.

1.1 Background to chosen theme

Tide Prediction Machines are analogue computers that were used to predict the times of high and low tides worldwide from the end of the 1800s up to the digital age. The first tide prediction machine was designed by William Thomson¹ (1824–1907), and was built in London in 1873. It was developed as a response to increasing pressure from commercial shipping lines towards the middle of the nineteenth century who wanted a greater number of more accurate tidal predictions more quickly than could be calculated by hand. As well as helping shipping lines and navies to safely navigate the seas and the shores, tide prediction machines became crucial to the building of ports and effective flood defences. A total of 25 of the 33 tide prediction machines ever built were constructed in the UK but were then shipped to other countries who wanted to do their own calculations. Although analogue tide prediction machines are no longer in use, most still exist today either in storage or as museum pieces across the world.

¹William Thomson is better known by the name Lord Kelvin, which he acquired when he was ennobled in 1892.

The history and development of tide prediction machines have been studied very little; previous work on this subject has concentrated on the use of tide prediction machines in the military or on tide prediction machines in the context of analogue computing machines. Two British oceanographers from whose writings I have learnt much are Dr. David Edgar Cartwright on the scientific history of tides (Cartwright 2000) and Prof. Philip Woodworth who compiled an inventory of all known tide prediction machines ever constructed (Woodworth 2016).

1.2 Background to chosen method

Prosopography is a research method usually used by historians to study the lives of groups of people. It involves the creation of a collective biography or the gathering of data relating to the common aspects of the lives of individuals who are part of a particular population. It can take the form of a database of all of the people within the chosen population along with information about the biographical phenomena that transcend their individual lives. Prosopography overcomes the problem of the scarcity of historical data by collecting together all available fragments, which can then be compared, synthesised and analysed, thus compensating for any gaps in the data. Instead of looking at the exceptional and unique, prosopography focuses on the general and average. It is in this way that prosopography makes visible the particular characteristics representative of the chosen population.

Prosopography is a well-established and documented historical research method. One resource that has been particularly useful is *A short manual to the art of prosopography* (Verboven, Carlier and Dumolyn 2007), which is a chapter that features in *Prosopography Approaches and Applications: A Handbook* (Keats-Rohan 2007).

1.3 Aims of research: research questions

The aim of this research project is bi-dimensional: there are historical objectives regarding tide prediction machines and methodological ones relating to prosopography.

1.3.1 Historical research objectives

Tide prediction machines performed life-saving calculations and made a crucial contribution to maritime history, but there is a lack of historical research into their existence and development. An historical research objective of this project is therefore to learn more about the importance and impact of tide prediction

machines and therefore raise awareness of them. Another objective is to facilitate the telling of the story of tide prediction machines. This will be achieved by studying them as a collection, rather than as individual artefacts. With these two objectives the aim is to provide a basis upon which existing exhibits of tide prediction machines can be improved and encourage an increase in the number of tide prediction machines that are on display rather than in storage.

1.3.2 Methodological research objectives

Until now, prosopography has mainly been used to study the lives of groups of people. Given the possible analogies between a group of a limited number of artefacts, all sharing common characteristics but each having a unique story from construction to eventual destruction, a methodological objective of this project is to examine whether prosopography can be successfully used to study the “lives” of groups of artefacts. A second methodological objective is to investigate how digital humanities tools can be used to facilitate a prosopography. These objectives will be fulfilled by applying prosopography to the group of 33 analogue tide prediction machines. In this way it will be demonstrated whether prosopography could be applied to the study of other groups of artefacts, and how it could be approached.

1.4 Outline of following chapters

This report takes the approach of first addressing the theory behind the theme and the method, combining both and executing a task to answer the research questions, and finally evaluating it and drawing conclusions. The historical sources and archives consulted for the project are detailed in chapter 2. The following chapter, chapter 3, explores the field of oceanography and the history of tidal prediction to understand the context in which tide prediction machines were developed. Chapter 4 studies prosopography and its potential, as well as digital humanities and how they can be of use, which is followed by the prosopographical study of tide prediction machines in chapter 5. Chapter 6 is a discussion and evaluation of the task undertaken in the previous chapter, and chapter 7 gives the conclusions of the project and perspectives for the future.

Chapter 2

Historical sources and resources

This section outlines the main sources and archives relating to the theme of tide prediction machines that have been used to write this report. They include journal articles, books, theses, reports, web resources, interviews with subject experts and primary sources in archives.

A scientific history of the tides is told in the scholarly work *Tides: a scientific history* by David E. Cartwright (Cartwright 2000), who was a world authority on the tides. His book discusses the advancement in understanding of tidal science throughout history, from the Megalithic period to today. Regarding the subject of this project, Cartwright's book explains the techniques used to predict the tides before, during and after the epoch of tide prediction machines. In particular he details the development of some of the first tide prediction machines to be constructed and also the eventual transition from these analogue machines to digital computers.

Oceanographer Philip L. Woodworth of the NOC has compiled an inventory of all analogue tide prediction machines ever built (Woodworth 2016). The inventory gives a description of every tide prediction machine in chronological order, including prototypes and portable machines, and includes photographs and diagrams where available. The descriptions include all or some of the following information: date and location of manufacture, name of manufacturer, machine architecture (number of components), dates and locations of operation, previous owners, date of decommissioning, current location and owner, current condition and whether it is currently on display to the public. Woodworth's inventory is an invaluable resource for this project as it is an assemblage of all known key information on every tide prediction machine known to be built. It also explains how the machines work and the science behind them, gives a brief history of previous inventories of tide prediction machines and describes the process of compiling this inventory.

A doctoral thesis of 2005 gives a detailed account of the more specific subject of tide tables, primitive and modern, from the eighth century to the present (P.

Hughes 2005). Methods of predicting the tides throughout history are explained, including those in use immediately before, after and during the epoch of tide prediction machines. Another paper on the history of tidal prediction techniques has been written by Jack R. Rossiter, ex-director of the Institute of Coastal Oceanography and Tides and internationally reputed for his research surrounding the tides. His article focuses on techniques used in the United Kingdom before the twentieth century (Rossiter 1971), which therefore includes the period leading up to and the first few years of the development of tide prediction machines. Other sources that contain information on tidal prediction throughout history include articles about weather and tidal forecasts over time (Pinaridi et al. 2017), the history of tidal studies (P. Hughes 2006), and the calculation, observation and mechanisation of tidal predictions (Durand-Richard 2016).

Tide prediction machines are discussed in a 2010 doctoral thesis on storm surge science at Liverpool Tidal Institute during the early- to mid-twentieth century (Carlsson-Hyslop 2010). This thesis gives useful information about how tide prediction machines were used, and who used and paid for the tide tables that were

Figure 2.1: The Roberts-Légé tide prediction machine, built 1908. Photograph taken by author at the Tide & Time exhibition, National Oceanography Centre, Liverpool, on 15 January 2019.

produced thanks to them. A more recent publication by the same author deals with tidal calculations in Great Britain during the First World War (Carlsson-Hyslop 2015). This paper analyses how the calculations were made and how the results were used for scientific, military and commercial ends, and to gain grants for the scientists involved.

The sources cited above are the key items identified during a review of existing literature relating to tide prediction machines. The search indicated that the history and development of tide prediction machines has not yet been studied, analysed and documented in a focused and continuous manner.

Figure 2.2: The Doodson-Légé tide prediction machine, built 1950. Photograph taken by author at the Tide & Time exhibition, National Oceanography Centre, Liverpool, on 15 January 2019.

During two research placements, at the archives of NML at their World Museum in Liverpool and at the archives of the SHOM at their main site in Brest, much relevant material was uncovered and examined. These archives contained diverse documents including correspondence between agents linked to the construction, purchase and use of tide prediction machines, annual reports of various institutions, advertising material concerning the sale of the machines, photographs of machines, locations and people, invoices and customs documents. Conversations during the placements with experts of tide prediction machines helped with the advancement of the project and gave different perspectives on the research.

NML now owns two tide prediction machines, both of which are on loan to the

NOC, Liverpool, for their exhibition *Tide & Time*¹ that showcases the role tidal science had in turning Liverpool into a major port and the city it is today. It is the only place in the world where you can see two of these machines together: the Roberts-Légé machine, built between 1906 and 1908 by Légé & Co. in London, and the Doodson-Légé machine, built in 1950 by the same company. They feature in figures 2.1 and 2.2. These two machines were installed at Bidston Observatory on the Wirral Peninsula in 1929 and in 1950 respectively, where they were used by Liverpool Observatory and Tidal Institute to predict the tides at national and international ports. Thanks to NML's recent renovation work the Doodson-Légé machine is exceptional for being in working order, as may be seen during a visit to the exhibition.

Figure 2.3: The Bidston-Kelvin tide prediction machine, built 1925. Photograph taken by author at the SHOM site in Brest on 18 December 2018.

The SHOM still has a British-made tide prediction machine, the Bidston-Kelvin machine as featured in a photograph in figure 2.3, that they acquired in 1950 and

¹Read more about the Tide & Time exhibition in an article written by the author for the British Society for the History of Science's online travel guide at <http://www.bsbs.org.uk/travel-guide-tide-time-exhibition-national-oceanography-centre-liverpool>.

Figure 2.4: Contents of a drawer on the side of the Bidston-Kelvin tide prediction machine. Photograph taken by author at the SHOM site in Brest on 18 December 2018.

used to predict the tides at overseas ports until 1966 (SHOM 2018). This machine remains a very complete artefact; it is thought to be in a state very similar to how it was left on the day of its decommissioning. The photograph in figure 2.4 shows the contents of a drawer in the side of the machine, which still contains spare parts, maintenance equipment and an instruction booklet.

Valerie Doodson and Sylvia Asquith both used to work with tide prediction machines at Bidston Observatory on the Wirral Peninsula in north west England, from 1952 to 1962 and from 1947 to 1990 respectively. They generously agreed to be interviewed to discuss their work with tide prediction machines and the evolution of their workplace².

²A blogpost written by the author about this experience can be consulted at <https://miehst1819.hypotheses.org/1221>.

Chapter 3

Oceanography and tidal prediction

3.1 What is oceanography?

Oceanography is a field of study within the Earth sciences that deals with the physical and biological properties and phenomena of the oceans and the seas. It is an interdisciplinary subject that is divided into four major sub-domains: biological oceanography, chemical oceanography, geological oceanography and physical oceanography (NOAA 2018b). Although these sub-domains are all intertwined, it is physical oceanography that is of most relevance to this work. Physical oceanography is the study of the physical conditions and processes in oceans and seas. It involves examining the transmission of light and sound through water and interactions between the ocean or the sea and its boundaries at the seafloor, the coast and the atmosphere. It also includes understanding and explaining the properties and motions of ocean and sea waters, such as waves, currents, eddies, gyres and tides (Britannica Library 2009).

3.1.1 The tides

Tides on Earth can be observed in bodies of water such as oceans, seas and lakes. Physically they appear as vertical movements of the surface of the water, the maximum and minimum of which are known as *high water* and *low water*, and alternating horizontal movements of the water, known as *tidal currents* (Gordon et al. 2015).

To understand why tides exist on Earth, it is first necessary to have some knowledge of the interactions between the Earth, the Moon and the Sun. The Moon is attracted to the Earth because of gravitational attraction but is also repulsed by the Earth due to the centrifugal force that results from the Moon spinning around it. The diagram in figure 3.1 shows the Earth (large circle on the left), the water on the surface of the Earth (oval) the Moon (small circle

on the right) and the forces in play between them: the red arrows represent the direction and the intensity of the force of gravitational attraction, the blue arrows represent the direction and the intensity of the centrifugal force and the green arrows represent the direction and the intensity of the resultant tide-causing force. The intensity of the centrifugal force on the Earth is constant whilst the intensity of the gravitational attraction varies proportionally to the changing distance between the Earth and the Moon. It is the combination of these two forces that results in the tides: when the resulting force is directed towards the centre of the Earth, the water level falls, and when the force is directed away from the centre of the Earth in the plane of the Moon, the water level rises, as shown by the green arrows in figure 3.1. The Sun contributes to tides on Earth in exactly the same way as the Moon does, but to a lesser extent. At most locations on Earth tides are semi-diurnal, which means that low tide and high tide each occur twice per day. This effect is a result of the rotation of the Earth itself and the fact that there is always high water on two opposite sides of the Earth at any one time. There is also a diurnal component to the tides, which is because of the asymmetry of the high water directed towards and away from the Moon (Ifremer 2004).

Figure 3.1: Diagram showing the forces in play between the Earth and the Moon. The red arrows represent the direction and the intensity of the force of gravitational attraction, the blue arrows represent the direction and the intensity of the centrifugal force and the green arrows represent the resultant tide-causing force. Not to scale. Diagram created by Vincent Lecoustey.

There are also certain geographical features on Earth that affect the height of the tides and their fluctuation in time. These features include the shape of the specific beach, the angle of the seabed leading up to the beach, the shape and depth of the surrounding coastline and the prevailing ocean currents (Byrd 2019). As well as these predictable astronomical and geographical tidal influences, the climate and weather have very unpredictable influences on the tides on Earth.

For all the astronomical, geographical and meteorological reasons aforementioned, the tides on Earth do not follow a repeated pattern (National Oceano-

graphy Centre 2019[b]). This means that the only way of knowing the times and heights of future tides is to forecast or predict them using an equation that takes into account the factors that cause them.

3.2 Importance of tidal prediction: then and now

As with many scientific theories, the development of tidal theory and methods of predicting the tides throughout history has been motivated by practical needs.

The most primitive reasons that motivated the search for methods of predicting times and heights of the tides include coastal dwelling, fishing and marine navigation. A need for tidal forecasts came with the development of ports, docks and harbours for their successful operation and management, and for coastal surveying. Engineers also started to make use of tidal predictions for coastal zone engineering projects, which include the construction and destruction of bridges and platforms. As for recreational activities, tidal forecasts are useful for beachgoers and for the safe practice of watersports, as well as for houseboat living. More precise predictions were called for as commercial shipping and naval operations evolved, and for the building of effective coastal and estuarine flood defences. Tidal predictions today are used for many more purposes than ever before. They are used by biologists and ecologists to better understand floating animals and plants, for habitat restoration projects and to study the effects of pollutants in bodies of tidal water (NOAA 2019). Tidal predictions and weather forecasts have a symbiotic relationship as the tides and the climate both affect each other, meaning that meteorologists make use of tidal predictions just as oceanographers make use of weather forecasts. The most recent use for tidal predictions is for harnessing tidal power, which can be converted into renewable energy.

3.3 History of tidal science and prediction

3.3.1 Before tide prediction machines

Tidal theory is the result of centuries of observations, hypotheses, empirical research and contributions from dozens of the brightest minds from a multitude of locations across the world.

The first attempts at predicting the tides were made by those occupying lands next to tidal waters in the form of rule-of-thumb methods linked to the phase of the moon. There is evidence from centuries and millennia before the Christian era of early Indian and Arabic civilisations recognising the influence of the moon over the tides, and of their interaction with and efforts to manage the tides (Cartwright 2000, p. 1-6). The Copernican Revolution, which stemmed from an

idea by Nikolaus Copernicus (1473–1543) that the Earth is not located at the centre of the universe but that it revolves around the Sun with other planets, allowed for the development of a new genre of physical theories of the tides from the sixteenth century. Distinguished polymaths and natural philosophers of the time such as Francis Bacon (1561–1626), Galileo Galilei (1564–1642), Johannes Kepler (1571–1630) and René Descartes (1596–1650) all contributed their theories of the tides, with varying levels of success (Cartwright 2000, p. 25-34). These attempts were eclipsed by a tidal theory by Isaac Newton (1643–1727), developed in the seventeenth century as part of his gravitational theory. The fundamental principles of Newton’s tidal theory remain in accordance with scientific understanding today, although some deductions drawn from them are erroneous (Cartwright 2000, p. 35). Around a century later and following many suggestions and modifications by other natural philosophers, Pierre-Simon de Laplace (1749–1827) proposed a *dynamic* theory of the tides, which for the first time took into account the dynamicity of the response of the ocean to tidal forces. Laplace translated his theory into a set of equations, today known as the *Laplace Tidal Equations*, which describe this dynamic response of the ocean (Cartwright 2000, p. 68-81).

3.3.2 From theories to analysis and prediction

The nineteenth century saw a shift in focus from tidal theories to the more practical analysis and prediction of tides. By expanding upon the base of data used by Laplace and making careful refinements to established theories, John William Lubbock (1803–1865) devised the so-called *synthetic* method of tidal analysis and prediction in the 1830s, which gave the most accurate predictions for tides at Liverpool at the time and therefore became the preferred method for calculating tide tables for British ports (Cartwright 2000, p. 91-92). The next significant advancement came in 1867 from Thomson in the form of a *harmonic* method of tidal analysis, based upon Laplace’s equations and works by Thomas Young (1773–1829) and George Biddell Airy (1801–1892) (Cartwright 2000, p. 82-83, 97). This development attracted the interest of the British Association for the Advancement of Science (BAAS)¹, who in the same year established a committee for the improvement and promotion of this newly discovered method (NOAA 2018a).

The harmonic method of analysis, based upon observations of sea levels (Pouvréau 2008, p. 37), allows for the individual factors causing the tides to be isolated as unique mathematical components and provides better results for a wider range of locations than the synthetic model, but is a much more complicated calculation. Its complexity meant that doing the calculation by hand was time-consuming and

¹The BAAS still exists today but has since changed its name to the *British Science Association*: <https://www.britishtscienceassociation.org>.

prone to errors, which was part of the motivation for devising a mechanical device capable of doing this calculation.

3.3.3 Development of tide prediction machines

The development of the first tide prediction machine was made possible thanks to funding from the BAAS who decided that calculations done by hand alone could no longer be relied upon to predict the tides at ports around the country. This was because of the increasing pressure from commercial shipping lines towards the middle of the nineteenth century, who wanted a greater number of more accurate predictions more quickly.

Figure 3.2: Kelvin's first operational tide prediction machine, built 1873. Photograph taken by author at the Science Museum, London, on 2 February 2019.

The first ever tide prediction machine was developed in Great Britain during a period when science and industry were growing closer together, a period of widespread mechanisation (Durand-Richard 2016, p. 127-128). However, the idea of a mechanical calculating machine was not new; Charles Babbage had already conceived the idea half a century earlier with his Difference Engine and Analytical

Engine (Dasgupta 2014, p. 22). More specifically, it is known that the design for the first tide prediction machine was inspired by a mechanical device devised by Charles Wheatstone for telegraphy purposes (Cartwright 2000, p. 104).

The construction of the first operational tide prediction machine, which features in a photograph in figure 3.2, was completed in 1873. It was designed by Thomson with the help of Edward Roberts and Alexander Lege, whose company *A. Lege & Co.* manufactured it in London (Woodworth 2016, p. 14). Lubbock’s synthetic method was relied upon for producing British tide tables until around 1920, by which time six further tide prediction machines had been constructed. These machines were primarily kept in Great Britain but were used to predict the tides at British colonial ports. Meanwhile, William E. Ferrel (1817–1891) and George Howard Darwin (1845–1912) were making modifications and improvements to Thomson’s harmonic method, and later Joseph Proudman (1888–1975) and Arthur Thomas Doodson (1890–1968) made significant contributions to tidal studies, and Doodson in particular to the improvement of tide prediction machines (Doodson 1921; Reidy 2008, p. 188). Eventually the transition from the synthetic method to the harmonic method in Great Britain was made, and thus the adoption of tide prediction machines for domestic ports (Cartwright 2000, p. 97-108).

3.3.4 How tide prediction machines work

The harmonic method of analysis uses a set of tidal observations² for any given location to isolate and identify every factor, known as a constituent, that contributes to the tides there. Each constituent is related to a different lunar or solar frequency with a known³ period T . The harmonic analysis allows for each constituent to be broken down into harmonic constants: an amplitude A and a phase ϕ , which are dependent on the chosen location. Inversely, harmonic tidal prediction involves summing each individual constituent that contributes to the tides at a chosen location and therefore requires the harmonic constants for that location to have already been calculated⁴. The more constituents taken into account in the calculation, the more accurate the prediction will be. Tide prediction machines use the harmonic method of prediction to calculate the times and heights of high and low tides at any moment in time and at any location in the world, provided the corresponding harmonic constants are known.

²Tidal observation refers to the act of continuously measuring the height of a body of water at any one location, usually using a tide gauge, to produce a set of tidal observations.

³The periods of the lunar and solar frequencies used in harmonic tidal analysis can be calculated using astronomical theories.

⁴Today there is almost no need to calculate harmonic constants as they are freely available online for most major ports worldwide.

$$H(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N} A_i \cos(\omega_i t - \phi_i) \quad (3.1)$$

Equation 3.1 shows the equation that tide prediction machines were designed to calculate (Bell 1962, p. 1; Woodworth 2016, p. 6). It sums over a finite number N of constituents i as a function of time t , where A_i is the amplitude of the constituent i , $\omega_i = 2\pi/T_i$ is the angular speed of the constituent i for which T_i is the period of the corresponding lunar or solar frequency, and ϕ_i is the phase of the constituent i . The equation gives as an output $H(t)$, which is the height of the water above ($H(t) > 0$) or below ($H(t) < 0$) the mean water level at time t . The times t at which the maxima and minima of $H(t)$ occur are the times of high and low tide respectively. The height of the water at any time is given by $H(t) + H_0$, where H_0 is the mean water level.

Tide prediction machines are made up of a system of pulleys, shown in a photograph in figure 3.3, each representing a different constituent. The pulleys simultaneously oscillate vertically and rotate. The period of each constituent is pre-programmed into the corresponding pulley, and the amplitude and phase of each pulley is set by the machine operator according to the harmonic constituents for the chosen location. A wire wound around the pulleys allows for the movement of the pulleys to be added, giving the output of the total rise or fall of the tide above the mean water level as a function of time for the programmed place. Not all tide machines were built the same but most operated on this principle and gave the outputs in the form of graphs, on dials or in displays.

Figure 3.3: Pulley system on the Doodson-Légé tide prediction machine, built 1950. Photograph taken by author at the Tide & Time exhibition, National Oceanography Centre, Liverpool, on 15 January 2019.

3.4 Tidal prediction today

Tidal predictions today are calculated using specially-made software that run on digital computers. They use the same harmonic method as the analogue machines of the last century, but are able to take into account many more constituents. The NOC has developed a software called POLTIPS-3 that can calculate predictions for anywhere in the world using up to 240 different constituents (National Oceanography Centre 2019[a]) whilst the SHOM uses a software called MAS that uses up to 541 constituents (Pouvreau 2008, p. 39-40).

3.5 Historical research questions

The historical research questions to be answered by this project are linked to three aspects of tide prediction machines: their architecture, locations and dates. This project will therefore investigate the evolution of tide prediction machine architecture, relations between locations of manufacture, operation and storage, and the significance of manufacture, operation and decommissioning dates. By learning more about their lives, it will be possible to have a greater understanding of their importance and impact and therefore why they should be conserved.

Chapter 4

Prosopography and digital humanities

4.1 What is prosopography?

Prosopography is usually used by historical researchers as a way of studying the lives of groups of people. It has been defined in many ways by various authors: H. De Ridder-Symoens defines prosopography as “a collective biography describing the external features of a population group that has something in common”; N. Bulst and J.-Ph. Genet define it as a method that “consists of describing the material characteristics of a more or less homogeneous group of persons”; L. Stone defines it as “the inquiry into common characteristics of a group of historical actors by means of a collective study of their lives”; N. Bulst has also defined it as “the database and the list of all persons from a specific milieu defined chronologically and geographically established preparatory to a processing of the prosopographical material from various historical angles” (Verboven, Carlier and Dumolyn 2007, p. 39).

4.1.1 Adaptation of prosopography to artefacts

Following the publication of the anthology *The social life of things: Commodities in cultural perspective* (Appadurai 1986), the study of “cultural biographies” of objects came into its own (Farago 2018). This field involves the study of the “life” of an object, from its fabrication and sale to its use and destruction (The Pitt Rivers Museum, University of Oxford 2013; University College London 2018), and could be applied to the objects to be studied in this project: analogue tide prediction machines. However, this approach would not take into account the multiplicity of the artefacts under consideration and would treat them as individual objects with

independent “lives”.

This prompts the idea that a collective “biography” of things could be a new application of prosopography. It has been done a few times before, for example to study the metallurgy of Early Bronze Age Britain and Ireland (Bray 2018), but the success of applying prosopography to artefacts has never been tested: that is one aim of this project.

It has been claimed that an application of prosopography to a group of anything other than people would not be a true prosopography, and that an attempt at applying prosopography to a group of artefacts is a way of doing multivariate analysis (Verboven, Carlier and Dumolyn 2007, p. 53). However, multivariate analysis can be considered as being more formal and less accessible than a prosopography of artefacts would be, and also does not facilitate the telling of the stories of the “lives” of the artefacts within the group; it is abstract and statistical.

In this project an analogy is being drawn between the life of a person and the existence of an artefact, supposing that every person and every artefact alike has a unique story to tell from the moment they enter the world to the moment they leave, and that every event that occurs and every relation that is established has an impact on an artefact just as it does on a person¹. A prosopography of artefacts is being defined for this project as the collective study of the biographies of all artefacts within a defined group, having collected all available fragments of data describing their lives (dates and locations of manufacture and use, names of manufacturers and users, dates of transportation, dates of sale, costs, date of decommissioning, post-working life location and status). It involves the creation of a database of all the data collected for each member of the group, which can be analysed in an attempt to answer historical questions about individual members of the group or the group as a whole. The members of the group of artefacts must have one or more features in common, such as function, geographic origin, user or date of invention.

4.1.2 How to do prosopography

If prosopography is the chosen method for a research project, the first step is to identify and define the group to be studied. Once the group has been determined it is necessary to construct working hypotheses and historical questions about the chosen group to be answered via the prosopography. These hypotheses and questions then need to be translated into a questionnaire that will be applied to every member of the group. Using authoritative sources, answers to as many parts of questionnaire as possible for every individual member of the group must be

¹Given the analogy being drawn, inverted commas will no longer be used when using traditionally person-oriented words in relation to artefacts.

found and then inputted to a systematic and uniform database. It then becomes possible to analyse the data in the database to attempt to prove or disprove the hypotheses and answer the original historical questions posed (Verboven, Carlier and Dumolyn 2007).

4.2 What is digital humanities?

Digital humanities is an interdisciplinary area of study that lies in the intersection between the humanities and digital technology. Research in digital humanities goes in two directions: it uses digital technologies to ask questions about and to create new knowledge in the humanities, and uses the humanities to ask questions of and to reflect upon digital technology. The digital technologies in digital humanities come in the form of tools, applications and software (purpose-built for digital humanities or not) that can be used for the effective production and dissemination of research in the humanities.

4.2.1 Digital humanities tools

Digital humanities tools can be useful in the three main stages of a research project: they can help with the advancement of research, the effective dissemination of results and the comprehension of results by the audience.

Different tools can facilitate the advancement of research by providing an environment in which data and research can be stored, managed and analysed. Data visualisation tools can highlight relationships within and between networks, help identify patterns, uncover and draw attention to trends previously hidden in the data, encourage the viewing of information in other ways and cause new enquiries to be made. Many digital humanities tools also offer a collaboration function, meaning that colleagues can work together simultaneously on the same file.

As for diffusing research findings, digital humanities can offer a wide range of platforms for presenting and sharing data, in many different ways.

Data presented in innovative formats make research more accessible and understandable by different types of learners. Visual representations can be better for younger audiences or those unfamiliar with a particular area of study because reading and interpreting visualisations of data can be easier and quicker than databases or text. Data in visual forms are also more attractive and more likely to be remembered, thereby facilitating their retelling.

Diverse digital humanities tools will be used in this project to associate, visualise and interpret the data, thereby distinguishing particular characteristics representative of tide prediction machines. The aim is to find and analyse the common features in the lives of tide prediction machines, which will give an appreciation of

their importance, the extent of their use and usefulness, and an impression of the shape of their lives.

4.3 Methodological research questions

A methodological research objective of this project is to assess whether prosopography can be successfully employed for the study of the lives of a group of artefacts. This will be done by conducting and evaluating a prosopography of tide prediction machines. Conducting a prosopography requires the collection, management and analysis of a large amount of data. It is for this reason that an objective of this project is to investigate how digital humanities tools can be used to facilitate a prosopography. This will be done by examining a range of digital humanities tools available, employing those suitable for the data and evaluating their usefulness. Chapter 5 is a complete prosopographical study of tide prediction machines conducted by the author that makes use of digital humanities tools and serves as the evidence required to test the two above research objectives.

Chapter 5

A prosopographical study of tide prediction machines

5.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines a complete prosopographical study of analogue tide prediction machines, conducted by the author. Its purpose is to provide a basis for answering the historical and methodological research questions detailed in sections 3.5 and 4.3 respectively. The prosopographical study has been conducted as per the definition given in section 4.1.1 and follows the guidelines given in section 4.1.2.

5.2 Definition of group

It is important to have a well-defined group with clear limits for a prosopography to be reliable. In the case of this project the group of artefacts is defined as non-portable mechanical tide-predicting analogue computing machines used worldwide for calculating tidal predictions from 1872 to 1990, when the last one was decommissioned.

5.3 Hypotheses and questions

The working hypotheses and historical questions to be considered in this prosopographical study are related to three themes, as specified in section 3.5. These three themes concern the architecture, locations of manufacture, operation and storage, and dates of manufacture, operation and decommissioning of tide prediction machines.

5.4 Collection and management of data

This prosopography is based almost entirely upon one comprehensive secondary source: Woodworth's inventory of tide prediction machines (Woodworth 2016). Woodworth is regarded as the world expert on tide prediction machines and many years of research have culminated in this inventory, making it very authoritative. Other sources and archives that were consulted for this project for verification and contextual purposes and are described in chapter 2.

The questionnaire created for the collection of data was composed of the following questions:

1. Name of machine
2. Name of manufacturer
3. Location of manufacture
4. Date manufacture began
5. Date manufacture ended
6. Names of operating organisations
7. Locations of operation
8. Dates of operation
9. Date of decommissioning
10. Current location
11. Current state
12. Current purpose

Responses to this questionnaire were entered into a custom database created using the software Numbers¹. A copy of the database can be found in appendix A.

¹Numbers is a spreadsheet application developed by Apple Inc. as part of the iWork productivity suite.

5.5 Data analysis

This project called for the use of digital humanities tools to aid with the data analysis process. An important detail to consider during the selection of such tools is the form of the data to be analysed. In this case the data are primarily in the forms of names, dates and locations. Following some research, the digital humanities tool chosen as most suited to this project was Palladio, an online application for the visualisation of complex historical data. A full review of Palladio is given in section 6.2.1. The research questions specified in section 5.3 will now be answered via the data analysis of the prosopography.

Figure 5.1: Graph showing variation of number of initial components built in tide prediction machines over time. Made by author using Numbers.

5.5.1 Machine architecture

As explained in section 3.3.4, the machines operate via a system of pulleys, each one referred to as a component representing a tidal constituent. The graph in figure 5.1, made with Numbers, shows a general increase in the number of initial components built in tide prediction machines over time, which can be attributed to a demand for more accurate predictions. However, the increase is not as step as might have been expected. This may be because of the extra cost in building

machines with more components and the lack of readiness to invest by importing countries².

5.5.2 Locations of manufacture, use, storage and display

Tide prediction machines were manufactured at a select few locations across the globe, but were only exported internationally by one country: Great Britain. The map in figure 5.2 shows that machines exported from Great Britain were destined for South America (Argentina, Brazil), South, Southeast and East Asia (India, Japan, Myanmar/Burma, Philippines, Thailand/Siam), and some parts of Europe (France, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Russia).

Figure 5.2: Map showing links between manufacture location (purple) and operation location (red) of tide prediction machines. Made by author using Palladio.

Around the time tide prediction machines were developed, Great Britain was just over half way through its “imperial century”, which lasted from 1815 to 1914,

²An example of such a reluctance towards investing in an overseas purchase is demonstrated in a letter of correspondence of 19 February 1948 from *Le Contrôleur des Dépenses Engagées* to *La Direction du Service Central Hydrographique*. This letter belongs to the SHOM archives and is located in TIDE PREDICTOR BOX 1/3.

during which time it added around 26 million square kilometres to its empire (Parsons 1999). The same period of time later became known as the *Pax Britannica*, and was a time when the British Royal Navy had power over the majority of shipping routes and established itself as the global hegemon (Porter 1999, p.332). The dominance of Great Britain gave it control over not only its colonial countries but also much of Asia and Latin America, as its “informal empire”, during this period and later (Porter 1999, p. 8; Marshall 1996, p. 156-157).

From the map in figure 5.2 it can be seen that the countries to which Great Britain exported tide prediction machines are largely those who were part of the British Empire, formally or informally, or those with whom it was an ally during either of the two world wars.

The network graph in figure 5.3 shows that only tide prediction machines manufactured in British cities were exported, and that those manufactured in London were mainly exported to the east, whilst those manufactured in Glasgow were mainly exported to the west.

Figure 5.3: Network graph showing network of locations of manufacture (dark grey) and locations of operation (light grey) of tide prediction machines worldwide. Points are sized relative to the number of machines manufactured or operated in each location. Made by author using Palladio.

5.5.3 Dates of manufacture, use and decommissioning

The first tide prediction machine was manufactured in 1872 and the last decommissioning of a tide prediction machine happened in 1990. The graph in figure 5.4 shows that the majority of tide prediction machines for which data are available had lifetimes of around 40 years, regardless of the location or time of manufacture. This graphic represents only eleven tide prediction machines because manufacture and decommissioning dates have not yet been found for the rest.

The graph in figure 5.5 shows that most tide prediction machines were made on an individual basis. It also shows that the First World War did not have much impact on tide prediction machine production but that the Second World War induced an interruption in manufacture during the fighting years, which were followed a few years of intense production.

Figure 5.4: Timespan showing dates of manufacture (bottom) and dates of decommissioning (top) of tide prediction machines worldwide. Line gradient represents length of lifetime. Made by author using Palladio.

Figure 5.5: Timeline showing number of tide machines that were finished being built each year worldwide. Made by author using Palladio.

Chapter 6

Discussion and evaluation

6.1 History and development of tide prediction machines

The prosopography was very successful in answering fundamental questions about the life-cycles of tide prediction machines, and in giving a wider and comparative view of the collection of machines as a whole. The study answered questions regarding the architecture, locations of manufacture, use, storage and display, and dates of manufacture, use and decommissioning of the machines. The most significant results include that the number of components initially built into the machines, and therefore the accuracy of their results, increased over time, that Great Britain exported tide prediction machines to countries with which it already had relationships, through its empire or otherwise, and that most machines had lifetimes of approximately forty years.

6.2 Success of artefact prosopography

The aim was to study these machines as a group of related artefacts rather than individual ones, which provided the study with a richer context allowing for wider conclusions to be drawn. Having precise questions to answer made the data collection element of the study very straightforward, especially as there were only 33 individual members in the artefact group and most of the data were available in just one document: Woodworth's inventory of tide prediction machines (Woodworth 2016). Managing the data was also straightforward, once again owing to the small number of members in the artefact group. However, more significant conclusions could be drawn with a larger group size. This prosopographic study was able to answer the questions asked of it owing to the amount of data collected

and linked together, and the use of digital humanities tools to analyse them.

Particularly owing to the use of digital humanities tools, the data had to be stored in a very methodical and uniform manner. The data analysis relied exclusively upon digital humanities tools, particularly for the visualisation of data, and they were key to the success of the prosopography. Another benefit of working with a small sample size in this trial prosopographic study of artefacts was that it was possible to verify the results given by the tools by direct interpretation of the data by eye; with a larger and more realistic group size that would not be possible. For this reason it is important to know how the tools work, for example by testing them such as has been done here, to ensure that they are being used correctly.

6.2.1 Application of digital humanities tools

Extensive use was made of digital humanities tools for this project, both for the visualisation and analysis of the data and for the writing and the diffusion of the research results. Such an abundance of digital humanities tools is available that the choice of ones to employ for the data analysis was almost overwhelming. Substantial effort had to be put in to research and test various tools before choosing the most suitable ones for the task at hand. However, the success of the prosopography depended largely on the use digital humanities tools for the storage, management, visualisation and analysis of the data.

All data visuals in chapter 5 were made by the author specifically for this project; they are new and original material. Although the data already existed, they have been greatly enhanced by translating it from raw numbers to images.

In this project, digital humanities tools were mainly used to visualise historical data. Visualising data helps the two most important types of people relating to any research project: the researchers and their audience.

For the researchers, benefits of visualising data include that creating diagrams of networks highlights relationships between and within them, plotting geospatial and temporal data visually makes it easier to spot patterns, and visualisations uncover and draw attention to trends previously hidden in the data. Data visualisations can help researchers to make the most of the available data at any point during the research process. They also give meaning to data and facilitate its comprehension by the audience. For the researchers' audience, advantages include that reading and understanding visualisations of data is easier and quicker, data in visual forms are more attractive and more likely to be remembered, and visuals facilitate the interpretation and retelling of data.

Palladio

Designed and built by Stanford University’s Humanities + Design Lab, Palladio¹ is a digital humanities tool for the visualisation of complex historical data. This free web-based open source application focuses on data-driven historical research. By modelling historical data, relationships across time and space can be analysed in an attempt to better understand the past.

Palladio is ideal for those who want to visualise networks, temporal data or geospatial data all from the same database using an intuitive graphical interface. Tabular data in various formats can be copied and pasted or uploaded to Palladio and then manipulated in many ways. It is important to ensure consistency in the data so that correct associations can be made between them, otherwise there is a risk of outputs being unrepresentative.

The graph function offered by Palladio can be used for visualising a network or networks and the relationships within and between them. The points can be filtered and sized according to other parameters in the database, which is why the initial database needs to be well thought out and constructed with Palladio in mind. An example of this type of graph made with Palladio can be found in figure 5.3.

To make use of the map function, Palladio requires data in the “latitude, longitude” format. These points can be plotted on a map of the world and can be coloured, sized, linked and filtered. The base map can also be changed to show different geographical elements, or a custom map can be uploaded. Such a map made with Palladio can be seen in figure 5.2.

The points displayed on a map or in a graph can be filtered by time, if the database contains data in a date format. Any date data can also be visualised with a timespan, which can have various different layouts, or with a timeline, which takes the form of a bar graph. Examples of a timespan and a timeline made with Palladio can be found in figures 5.4 and 5.5 respectively. However, Palladio does not allow the adding of legends, titles or colours to graphs, timespans or timelines, which is a significant restriction.

Palladio does not store any user data but anything created on Palladio can be downloaded as a .json file and then uploaded and modified at a later date. Graphs, map points, timespans and timelines can also be downloaded as .svg image files.

Palladio is an excellent example of a digital humanities tool that can be used by historians to visualise data, although its limits quickly become evident. Most of the functions available have been used and demonstrated through this project. From a single database, researchers can create various visual elements that are to a certain extent personalisable according to the data available. Palladio it creates

¹The Palladio web application can be found at <http://hdlab.stanford.edu/palladio>.

visuals but leaves the analysis to the user. Unfortunately only the map could be coloured; being able to colour parts of the graphs, timespans and timelines would be very useful and attractive. Another key element lacking is the ability to create titles or legends for the visuals. Palladio can be regarded as a stepping-stone to more complex data visualisation software as it allows the user to explore the potential of a dataset in question by producing simple visualisations quickly and easily.

Time.Graphics

Founded by Evgeny V. Mustafin, Time.Graphics² is a web-based tool for the creation of timelines. Although it is a commercial service, many features are available free of charge with an account. The intuitive graphical interface can be used by students, teachers and businesses for project planning, data analysis, biographies, goal attainment and data visualisation.

Timelines created using Time.Graphics can span from billions of years to a few hours. Timestamps to the nearest minute can be given to single events or timespans added to the timeline, along with a title, description, colour and photo. Timelines can be downloaded in various image formats, and the data can be downloaded in the form of a spreadsheet. A timeline created with Time.Graphics for this project can be seen in appendix B.

²The online Time.Graphics service can be found at <https://time.graphics>.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and perspectives

7.1 Summary

The aims of this project were bi-dimensional: on the one hand historical and on the other methodological. The historical objective included raising awareness of the importance and impact of tide prediction machines and making telling the story of tide prediction machines more efficient by learning more about their lives. A secondary objective was to encourage the public display of tide prediction machines and to supply material with which existing exhibits could be improved. The methodological objective included investigating whether prosopography could be successfully applied to groups of artefacts, as opposed to people, and how to use digital humanities tools to facilitate the process. This had the end goal of developing a revised method for studying groups of artefacts by making use of tools already available.

In an attempt to achieve the aims of this project, guidelines and principles were developed and established to describe a prosopography of artefacts instead of people. This artefact prosopography was tested by applying it to tide prediction machines. In this way it was possible to evaluate both the artefact prosopography approach and examine the history and development of tide prediction machines: the two main objectives of this project.

7.2 Findings

The artefact prosopography of tide prediction machines produced a number of interesting results, in particular concerning the machine architecture, their locations and significant dates, through the use of digital humanities tools to analyse data. Regarding machine architecture, it was demonstrated that the number of components initially built in tide prediction machines gradually increased with time. As

for the locations of manufacture, use, storage and display of the machines, it was shown that the majority of machines were manufactured in Great Britain, and that these machines were often exported to countries that had relationships with Great Britain. The result is that tide prediction machines were used at locations across the world, and many of them still exist today in storage or on display to the public. Regarding the dates of manufacture, use and decommissioning of the machines, it was shown that the Second World War had an impact on production levels and that most machines had working lifetimes of forty years.

Artefact prosopography has been demonstrated as having the potential to be used in further projects that aim to study a collection of related objects. Considering artefacts as part of a group gives an extra dimension to a study that doesn't exist if only one individual artefact is studied in isolation. Definitions and guidelines for an artefact prosopography were given in sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2, and an example of a real application of artefact prosopography was given in chapter 5.

7.3 Diffusion

Intermediary stages of this research were presented by the author at the International Port and Maritime Studies Network Annual Conference 2019¹ in Dundee, 24-25 April 2019 (5 minute speed lecture), and at the DARIAH-EU Annual Event 2019² in Warsaw, 15-17 May 2019 (poster presentation). This project is due to be presented by the author at Shaped by the Sea³ in Manchester, 27-28 June 2019 (20 minute presentation), and at the Oceanext Interdisciplinary Conference 2019⁴ in Nantes, 3-5 July 2019 (20 minute presentation). The poster and abstracts for the presentations listed above can be consulted in appendix C. The author also published a short video summary of the project on YouTube⁵.

7.4 Future perspectives

This project concerned the activity of producing data with tide prediction machines for a wide range of users; an activity that concerns a wide range of actors. A future

¹The International Port and Maritime Studies Network Annual Conference 2019 programme can be consulted at <https://ippmsn.wordpress.com/2019/04/04/ippmsn-programme-2019>.

²The DARIAH-EU Annual Event 2019 website can be consulted at <https://dariah-ae-2019.sciencesconf.org>.

³The Shaped by the Sea programme can be consulted at <https://blogs.manchester.ac.uk/chstm/2019/06/04/shaped-by-the-sea-conference-27-28th-june-2019>.

⁴The Oceanext Interdisciplinary Conference 2019 website can be consulted at <https://oceanext-2019.sciencesconf.org>.

⁵The video summary of this project can be viewed at <https://youtu.be/DmxLUB8g10Q>.

study of tide prediction machines could look more closely at the actors involved and the notion of activity implied. It would be possible to conduct a prosopographic study of all actors who have had some involvement with tide prediction machines, be it in their production, use or conservation, and then combining the actor-centric and the artefact-centric prosopographies to achieve the most complete analysis.

Despite the success of this prosopographical study of artefacts, the process would have to be repeated with different artefacts and with different goals to ensure the suitability of prosopography for studying groups of artefacts. An artefact prosopography would also benefit from a sample size considerably larger than 33, as was used in this project, and from having an ontology, given the nature of the data in this type of research. A good candidate would be the ontological approach proposed as part of the research work developed at the CFV in Brest in collaboration with the CERV on the subject of “the comparative history of maritime cultural landscapes and digital humanities” in Brest, Venice, Argentina, Chile, Saint Pierre and Miquelon and the Îles du Ponant. The maritime landscape is considered to be a Large Technological System, according to a definition proposed by Thomas P. Hughes (Bijker, T. P. Hughes and Pinch 1987). A temporal evolution model of these landscapes focused on human activity and called ANY-ARTEFACT has been developed from James H. Bird’s geographical ANYPORT model (Rodrigue 2017). It is based on the choice of artefacts as characteristic indicators of human activity linked, for example, to mobility (bridges, cranes, etc.) or industrial production (forges, rope mills, etc.)⁶.

An exciting prospect for tide prediction machines would be the creation of a virtual environment in which it is possible to operate a tide prediction machine and interact with a knowledgeable avatar. Such an environment could be installed in museums to make a virtual exhibit or used in conferences or schools for educational purposes. It would require the input of experts in visual environments, much more detailed data collection on tide prediction machines and the creation and use of an interoperable ontology for the avatar.

There exist many types of knowledge, but this project has focused on the explicit kind. By speaking with those who have interacted with tide prediction machines, such as those already included in this project, it would be possible to uncover some tacit knowledge related to manipulation of the machines, human know-how and handiwork. In this way human activity could be reconstituted and integrated into a virtual environment⁷. It could also be interesting, with the approval of those involved, to create a video archive of Valerie Doodson and Sylvia Asquith talking about their experience working with tide prediction machines.

⁶See the thesis works of Bruno Rohou: <https://brmdp.hypotheses.org>, and Marie-Morgane Abiven: <https://brestvenise.hypotheses.org>, both of the CFV, Brest.

⁷See the thesis work of Marie-Morgane Abiven: <https://brestvenise.hypotheses.org/6>.

Such a project could also touch on the subject of gender and women in the workplace in the twentieth century.

As well as creating a virtual model of a tide prediction machine, another possibility would be to build a working model of one using a 3D printer⁸. Once the design had been finalised it could be shared and printed on any other 3D printer, meaning that models could be made available and put on display anywhere in the world.

⁸A working 3D-printed model of one of James Watt's steam engines has been built by a team of University of Glasgow students: https://www.gla.ac.uk/news/headline_649972_en.html; the same technique could be applied to a tide prediction machine.

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Appendix A

Tide prediction machine database

A database containing data relating to the prosopographic study of tide prediction machines was created by the author using Numbers, a spreadsheet software. A copy of the database is included on the next page.

Appendix B

Tide prediction machine timeline

A timeline¹ showing life events of all tide prediction machines manufactured in Great Britain was created by the author using Time.Graphics, a digital humanities tool. A copy of the timeline is included on the next page.

¹The timeline can be consulted at <https://time.graphics/line/180223>.

Appendix C

Conference abstracts and poster

C.1 International Port and Maritime Studies Network Annual Conference 2019

A 5 minute speed lecture with slides¹ was given by the author during the International Port and Maritime Studies Network Annual Conference 2019 in Dundee, 24-25 April 2019. The abstract, written by the author, follows.

A New Wave of Prosopography: an Application to Tide Prediction Machines

Tide Prediction Machines (TPMs) are analogue computers that were used to predict the times of high and low tides worldwide from the end of the 1800s up to the digital age. The first TPM was designed by William Thomson and built in London in 1873. It was developed as a response to increasing pressure from commercial shipping lines towards the middle of the 19th century who wanted a greater number of more accurate tidal predictions more quickly than could be calculated by hand. As well as helping shipping lines and navies to safely navigate the seas and the shores, TPMs became crucial to the building of ports and effective flood defences. Most of the 33 TPMs ever built were constructed in the UK but were then shipped to other countries who wanted to do their own calculations. In this research, prosopography is used to analyse the life cycle of TPMs, from the motivation for producing them to their decommissioning and their status today. Prosopography is a research approach usually used by historians to study the lives of groups of people; only recently has the idea of conducting prosopographical studies of collections of related objects begun to be explored. This is a concept that is developed and utilised in this research. The aim is to find and analyse the

¹The slides can be viewed and downloaded at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3003566>.

common features in the lives of TPMs, which will give an appreciation of their importance, the extent of their use and usefulness, and an impression of the shape of their lives.

C.2 DARIAH-EU Annual Event 2019, Warsaw, 15-17 May 2019 (poster presentation)

A poster² entitled *Tide Prediction Machines, Prosopography and Digital Humanities: what are they and how do they fit together?* was presented by the author during the DARIAH-EU Annual Event 2019 in Warsaw, 15-17 May 2019. The poster is based on a blog post³ of the same title written by the author. The author won the Digital Humanities Tools and Methods Blog Competition 2019⁴ run by DARIAH-EU with this blog post. The prize was a 500 € scholarship to attend the DARIAH-EU Annual Event 2019 and the opportunity to present a poster there. A copy of the poster, created by the author, is included on the next page.

²The poster can be viewed and downloaded in high-resolution at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2908250>.

³The blog post can be consulted at <https://dhmethods.hypotheses.org/229>.

⁴Details of the competition can be consulted at <https://dhmethods.hypotheses.org/215>.

Tide Prediction Machines, Prosopography and Digital Humanities: what are they and how do they fit together?

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Cultural history of science and technology, digital humanities and mediation

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Tide Prediction Machines

- Analogue computers for calculating predictions of times of high and low tides
- Preceded by long calculations by hand, succeeded by digital computers
- First operational tide prediction machine constructed in London in 1873
- 25 out of 33 machines ever built constructed in UK
- Many machines exported; used worldwide

British Tide Predictor No. 1, built in London in 1873, now on display at London Science Museum. Photograph taken by H. M. Rawsthorne on 02/02/19.

Bidston Kelvin machine, built in Glasgow in 1924-25, now at SHOM site in Brest (France). Photograph taken by H. M. Rawsthorne on 18/12/18.

Doodson-Légé machine, built in London in 1950, now on display at NOC site in Liverpool (UK). Photograph taken by H. M. Rawsthorne on 15/01/19.

A New Wave of Prosopography: an Application to Tide Prediction Machines

THE PROJECT

- Study lives of tide prediction machines by doing a prosopography of them
- Analyse use and impact of tide prediction machines
- Investigate status of machines today
- Make it easier to tell the story of lives of tide prediction machines

THE QUESTIONS

- Can prosopography successfully be used to study a group of artefacts?
- How can digital humanities tools be used to facilitate a prosopographical study?

Prosopography

- Research method usually used to study lives of groups of people
- Overcomes problem of scarcity of historical data by collecting together all available fragments and analysing them, thus compensating for gaps in the data
- Highlights particular characteristics representative of chosen group
- Focuses on the general and average instead of the exceptional and unique

Use of digital humanities

THE DATA

- Most data is temporal and geospatial (dates and locations of manufacture, operation, decommissioning, etc.)
- Some numerical data (number of constituents on machines, cost of machines, etc.)
- Some textual data (names of machines, manufacturers, etc.)

Palladio (right)

- Map (right) shows journeys made by tide prediction machines during their lifetimes, from manufacture location to operation location
- Timespan (below, right) shows lifetimes of tide prediction machines
- Different visualisations uncover patterns previously hidden in data

WHY DH TOOLS?

- Storage and management
- Association and analysis
- Visualisation and interpretation
- Presentation and diffusion

WHICH DH TOOLS?

- Zotero (bibliography management)
- CmapTools (mind map creator)
- Palladio (complex data visualiser)
- Time.Graphics (timeline creator)
- Hypotheses (blog platform)
- Twitter (social network)
- Overleaf (Latex editor)

Time.Graphics (above)

- Timeline shows significant dates of tide prediction machines built in UK: manufacture date, displacements, renovations, prizes awarded and decommissioning
- Each individual machine assigned different colour to aid identification on timeline
- Interpreting and comparing data easier with colourful and visual representation

Helen Mair Rawsthorne

Winner of DARIAH's DH methods and tools blog competition 2019

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C.3 Shaped by the Sea

A 20 minute presentation with slides will be given by the author during the Shaped by the Sea conference in Manchester, 27-28 June 2019. The abstract, written by the author, follows.

The Development of Tide Prediction Machines

Tide Prediction Machines (TPMs) are analogue computers that were used to predict the times of high and low tides worldwide from the end of the 1800s up to the digital age. The first TPM was designed by William Thomson (later Lord Kelvin) and built in London in 1873. It was developed as a response to increasing pressure from commercial shipping lines towards the middle of the 19th century who wanted a greater number of more accurate tidal predictions more quickly than could be calculated by hand. As well as helping shipping lines and navies to safely navigate the seas and the shores, TPMs became crucial to the building of ports and effective flood defences. Most of the 33 TPMs ever built were constructed in the UK but were then shipped to other countries who wanted to do their own calculations. Oceanographers Joseph Proudman and Arthur Doodson of Liverpool Observatory and Tidal Institute contributed significantly to the development of tidal analysis and to the evolution of TPMs. They and the institution thus gained a worldwide reputation for tidal research and prediction. TPMs were always operated on land, in some cases over 1000 km from the nearest sea or ocean. Prosopography is a research approach usually used by historians to study the lives of groups of people. Given the analogies with human groups, the research hypothesis is that it is possible to apply prosopographic methods to analyse the life cycle of TPMs, from the motivation for producing them to their status after decommissioning and replacement by newer technology. The aim is to find and analyse the common features in the lives of TPMs, which will give an appreciation of their importance, the extent of their use and usefulness, and an impression of the shape of their lives.

C.4 Oceanext Interdisciplinary Conference 2019

A 20 minute presentation with slides will be given by the author during the Shaped by the Oceanext Interdisciplinary Conference 2019 in Nantes, 3-5 July 2019. The abstract, written by the author and Sylvain Laubé, follows.

A New Wave of Prosopography: an Application to Tide Prediction Machines

Tide Prediction Machines (TPMs) are analogue computers that were used to predict the times of high and low tides worldwide from the end of the 1800s up to the digital age. The first TPM was designed by William Thomson and built in London in 1873. It was developed as a response to increasing pressure from commercial shipping lines towards the middle of the 19th century who wanted a greater number of more accurate tidal predictions more quickly than could be calculated by hand. As well as helping shipping lines and navies to safely navigate the seas and the shores, TPMs became crucial to the building of ports and effective flood defences. A total of 25 of the 33 TPMs ever built were constructed in the UK but were then shipped to other countries who wanted to do their own calculations. Although analogue TPMs are no longer in use, most still exist today either in storage or as museum pieces across the world⁵.

The methodological approach proposed is part of the research work developed at the Centre F. Viète in Brest, in collaboration with the Centre Européen de Réalité Virtuelle (CERV) on the subject of “comparative history of maritime cultural landscapes and digital humanities”⁶ (Brest, Venice, Argentina, Chile, Saint Pierre and Miquelon, Iles du Ponant).

In this project, the maritime landscape is considered as a Large Technological System (LTS) according to a definition proposed T. P. Hughes⁷. A temporal evolution model of these landscapes focussed on human activity and called ANY-ARTEFACT has been developed from Bird’s geographical ANYPORT model⁸. It is based on the choice of artefacts as characteristic indicators of human activity linked, for example, to mobility (bridges, cranes, etc.) or industrial production (forges, rope mills, etc.)⁹. The work in progress presented here concerns the activity of producing data with TPMs for a wide range of users.

Prosopography is a research approach usually used by historians to study the

⁵Philip Woodworth, *An inventory of tide prediction machines* (Southampton: National Oceanography Centre, 2016), <http://nora.nerc.ac.uk/id/eprint/513660>.

⁶Sylvain Laubé, Ronan Querrec, Marie-Morgane Abiven and Serge Garlatti, “Lab In Virtuo : Un environnement Virtuel Intelligent (EVI) participatif dédié à l’histoire et aux patrimoines des paysages culturels industriels,” (presented at #dhnord2018: *Matérialités de la recherche en sciences humaines et sociales*, Lille, October 2018), <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01950624>.

⁷Wiebe E. Bijker, Thomas P. Hughes, and Trevor J. Pinch, eds., *The social construction of technological systems: New directions in the sociology and history of technology* (Cambridge, MA: MIT press, 1989).

⁸The Geography of Transport Systems, “The Evolution of a Port (The Anyport Model),” accessed 28 March 2019, https://transportgeography.org/?page_id=3388.

⁹See thesis works of Bruno Rohou, <https://brmdp.hypotheses.org>, and Marie-Morgane Abiven, <https://brestvenise.hypotheses.org>.

lives of groups of people¹⁰. Human activity is studied according to three main axes: the material system of artefacts, the actors, and the knowledge involved. The 33 machines form a coherent group in which each artefact can be described by its “life cycle” (i.e. a time evolution cycle modelled from ANY-ARTEFACT). Given the analogies with human groups, the research hypothesis is that it is possible to apply prosopographic methods to analyse the “life cycle” of TPMs, from the motivation for producing them to their decommissioning and their status today.

Diverse digital humanities tools are being used to associate, visualise and interpret the data, thereby distinguishing particular characteristics representative of TPMs. The aim is to find and analyse the common features in the lives of TPMs, which will give an appreciation of their importance, the extent of their use and usefulness, and an impression of the shape of their “lives”.

This ongoing work is part of a collaboration with the SHOM (Brest) and the Musée des Arts et Métiers (Paris). It is also part of the research areas of the GIS d’Histoire Maritime¹¹ and the Data for History Consortium¹².

¹⁰Koenraad Verboven, Myriam Carlier and Jan Dumolyn, “A Short Manual to the Art of Prosopography,” in *Prosopography Approaches and Applications: A Handbook*, ed. Katharine. S. B. Keats-Rohan (Oxford: University of Oxford Linacre College Unit for Prosopographical Research, 2007), 35–69, <https://prosopography.history.ox.ac.uk/images/01%20Verboven%20pdf.pdf>.

¹¹GIS d’Histoire Maritime, “GIS d’histoire maritime,” accessed 28 March 2019, <http://www.histoire-maritime.org>.

¹²Data for History, “Data for History Consortium,” accessed 28 March 2019, <http://dataforhistory.org>.